

Production and optimization of amylase by *B.megaterium* RBJ (KM234609) using wheat bran

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Abstract

Several bacterial isolates were isolated from soil samples near rice mill industries were capable to grow and produce amylase. Among these isolates, BS4 was found to produce the highest amylase activity on productive medium supplemented with 1% starch at 37°C for 24 hours. This isolate was identified as *Bacillus megaterium* strain RBJ according to phenotypic tests and was confirmed by 16S rRNA gene sequencing. Amylase production from *B.megaterium* strain RBJ could be improved by controlling various physical and nutritional factors for rapid identification of the process parameters and development of optimum culture conditions. The amylase production by the test bacterial strain through solid state fermentation (SSF) using wheat bran as a substrate was found to be accelerated at optimized culture conditions such as different incubation time, temperature, pH, agitation speed, inoculum size, different carbon and nitrogen sources, amino acids and metal ions. From the result it could be concluded that, the incubation time of 48h, temperature 40°C, pH7, agitation speed with 150 rpm, inoculum size of 1ml, 1% starch, 1% peptone, 0.02% tryptophan and 0.1% CaCl₂ were optimum for maximum amylase production.

Keywords Amylase, *Bacillus megaterium*, solid state fermentation, wheat bran, optimization

Introduction

In industrial sectors, bacterial and fungal sources have been increasingly applied for enzyme production is an age-old technology (Pandey et al. 2000, Ravindran et al. 2018,). The biochemical diversity, short growth period, stability over pH and temperature ranges and the ease with which enzyme concentrations might be increased by environmental and genetic manipulation made the microbial production of amylase more fruitful than that of other sources like plant or animals (Oliveira et al. 2007; Mishra and Behera 2008, Niyonzima et al. 2020).

Amylases are enzyme which hydrolyze starch molecules to give diverse products including dextrin and progressively smaller polymers composed of glucose units (Windish and Mhatre 1965). Amylases account for 65% of enzyme market in the world (Balkan and Figen 2007). Amylases are commercially employed in paper, textile, brewing and pharmaceutical industries. The production of enzymes under enhanced conditions to get desirable properties of enzymes is a continuous exercise (Francois 2019). Therefore, low cost medium is necessary for the production of amylase to meet the demands of these industries (Balkan and Figen 2007; Abd-Elhalem et al. 2015).

The genus *Bacillus* produces a large variety of extracellular enzymes, of which amylases and proteases are of significant industrial importance (Prakash and Jaiswal 2009). Among the large microbial population, screening provides an opportunity to detect and isolate only those microorganisms of interest through highly selective procedures (Madhav et al. 2011).

The production of amylase by solid state fermentation (SSF) is a preferred method and influenced by a variety of physiochemical factors (Arnau et al. 2019). To meet the growing demands of the industry, it is necessary to improve the performance of the system and thus increase the yield without increasing the cost of production (Gangadharan et al. 2008). A number of agro industrial residues are generally considered as the best substrates for solid state fermentation. Sugar cane bagasse, wheat bran, rice bran, maize bran, gram bran, wheat straw, corn cobs, banana waste, palm oil mill waste, sugar beet pulp, coconut oil cake, wheat flour, corn flour etc. are some of the substrates that have been used for enzyme production (Pandey et al. 1994; Selvakumar et al. 1998).

The objective of this study was to isolate and identify the amylolytic bacteria through conventional and molecular characterization technique and to investigate the agro industrial residues as an alternative carbon source to produce amylase and to optimize various physical and nutritional factors on amylase production by solid state fermentation.

Materials and Methods

Screening and identification of amylase producing bacteria

Sample collection

Soil samples were collected from rice milling industries in and around Kanyakumari district, Tamilnadu. Soil samples were collected from subsurface of 2 to 3 cm depth by using sterile spatula, and then transferred in to sterile bags (Rakaz et al,2021).

Isolation of bacteria

Isolation of bacteria was done by serial dilution method. 1 gm of the soil was serially diluted in sterile distilled water at a concentration range of 10^{-1} to 10^{-4} . A volume of 0.1ml from each dilution was transferred aseptically to nutrient agar plates. The samples were uniformly spreaded on the plate using an L-rod. Then the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hr. The bacterial isolates were subcultured in the respective media in order to obtain pure culture. Pure cultures were stored at 4°C for further studies.

Primary screening of Amylase producing bacteria

10 gm of soluble starch is dissolved in 100ml of distilled water by applying heat. After complete dissolution of starch 20 ml of the solution was mixed in 100ml of melted nutrient agar and poured into the petri dish after sterilization. A loop full of fresh bacterial culture was picked by a sterile loop and stabbed on to agar plate. After 24 hours of incubation at 37°C, the plates were flooded with dilute iodine solution. Hydrolysis of starch was indicated by a clear zone around the growth and unchanged starch gave a violet-blue colour around the colony about 2mm. Upon such a result the bacterial isolates were selected for further experimental studies (Collins et al,1995).

Identification of amylase producing bacteria

Based on the color, shape, size, nature of colony and pigmentation, totally 27 different bacterial colonies were isolated and the isolates were individually subjected for primary screening to determine their amylase production capability using starch agar medium. The amylase producing bacteria were initially identified up to genus level based on their morphological, physiological and biochemical characteristics (Holt et al. 1994). Qualitative determination of amylase production was performed using well cut or cup assay with some modifications (Sudharhsan et al. 2007). Among the eleven strains, maximum amylase producer was further identified up to species level through 16S rRNA sequencing.

Screening of agriculture by products as substrates for SSF

Ten agricultural residues such as rice bran (RB), jack fruit seed (JFS), banana peel (BP), potato peel (PP), tamarind seed (TS), wheat bran (WB), tapioca peel (TP), corn cobs (CC), orange peel (OP) and sugar beet peel (SP) were taken as solid substrate. For the production, 5g each of the individual dry substrates were taken into an Erlenmeyer flasks (250ml) and added with 2ml of salt solution (KH_2PO_4 - 2g, NaCl - 1g, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - 1g, distilled water - 1000ml and pH - 7). The contents of flasks were mixed and autoclaved at 121°C for 15min. After sterilization, 1% of inoculum was inoculated into each substrate and incubated at 37°C for 48h. After incubation, the enzyme was extracted in 50ml of 0.1M phosphate buffer (pH6.5) on a rotary shaker at 150rpm for 30min. The content was filtered through muslin cloth, and then the filtrate was centrifuged at 8000rpm for 10min. The supernatant was filtered through Whatmann number 1 filter paper and the filtrate was used as the crude enzyme preparation. Finally the amylase activity was estimated following the methodology proposed by Miller (1959).

Optimization of culture conditions for solid state amylase production

Optimization of process parameters was studied using wheat bran as the best substrate for solid state fermentation. The amylase production was optimized by varying physical parameters such as the incubation period, temperature, pH, agitation speed, moisture content and inoculum size; nutritional parameters such as carbon, nitrogen, amino acid, metal ions sources and surfactants.

Effect of physical parameters

The effect of different incubation time on amylase production was determined by incubating the test bacterial strain in solid medium (wheat bran) at different time intervals of 24, 48, 72, 96, 120 and 144h in a shaker (150rpm) at 37°C. To access the effect of temperature for maximum amylase production, the substrate inoculated with bacterial culture was incubated at various temperatures (10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70 and 80°C). To investigate the effect of different pH on amylase production by the test bacterial strain, the solid medium was set at different pH ranges of 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11 and 12 and incubated at 37°C for 48h. The optimum agitation speed required for amylase production in solid medium was determined at various agitation speeds (50, 100, 150, 200, 250, and 300 rpm). To determine the influence of different moisture content of the substrate, it was optimized under various moisture contents (10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70 and 80%) and incubated at 37°C for 48h. To check the effect of different inoculum size of test bacterial strain on amylase production, different volumes (0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 2.5, 3, 3.5, 4, 4.5 and 5 ml) of inoculum was inoculated in individual flask and incubated at 37°C for 48h. After incubation, the amylase production was estimated from the culture supernatant by spectrophotometric assay method (Miller 1959).

Effect of nutritional parameters

Different carbon sources (1%w/v glucose, sucrose, lactose, fructose, maltose, galatose, starch, dextrin, glycerol, xylose, mannitol and ribose), nitrogen sources (1%w/v tryptone, casein, gelatin, peptone, yeast extract, urea, ammonium hydrogen phosphate, ammonium nitrate, ammonium sulphate, ammonium chloride, sodium nitrate and potassium nitrate), amino acids (0.02%w/v glycine, L - lysine, L - tyrosine, L - cysteine, L - alanine, L - phenylalanine, L - isoleusine, L - valine, L - methinine, tryptophan and glutamic acid) and metal ions (0.1% MgCl₂, MnCl₂, FeCl₃, CaCl₂, CoCl₂, ZnCl₂, MgSO₄, NaCl, MnSO₄, CuSO₄, ZnSO₄ and HgCl₂) were employed to determine their influence on solid state amylase production.

Statistical analysis

The data obtained in the present study were expressed as Mean \pm SD and were analyzed using One way ANOVA test at 5% level of significance using computer software statistica 6.0 (Statsoft, Bedford, UK).

Result and discussion

Screening and identification of amylase producing bacteria

Totally 27 (BS1 to BS27) different morphologically dissimilar colonies were isolated and the strength of extracellular amylase production by all the isolated bacterial colonies was screened individually for their ability to produce amylase in starch agar. Among the 27 isolates, only 11 isolates (BS4, BS5, BS7, BS9, BS13, BS14, BS15, BS19, BS22, BS23 and BS25) were the producers of amylase in starch agar (Fig. 1). Alpha amylase can also be produced by different species of microorganisms, but for commercial applications α -amylase is mainly derived from the genus *Bacillus*, fungi as well as in plant (Souza and Magalhaes 2010, Indrakshi et al. 2019). Similarly in the present study, most of the isolates (6 no's) were belonging to the genera *Bacillus*. The remaining 5 isolates were *Micrococcus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Streptococcus* sp., *Serratia* sp., and *Klebsiella* sp. Among 11 amylase producing positive isolates, the isolate *Bacillus* sp. (BS4) showed maximum amylase production in the zone formation of 29.33 ± 1.527 mm by hydrolyzing starch agar medium.

Fig. 1 Primary screening of amylase producing bacterial strains using starch agar plate

The 16S rRNA sequencing of this *Bacillus* sp. (BS4) showed 99% similarity with *Bacillus megaterium*. Thus the test bacterial strain (BS4) was identified as *Bacillus megaterium* strain RBJ and it was submitted to GenBank in NCBI database under the accession number KM234609.

Screening of agriculture byproducts as substrates for SSF

In SSF, the selection of a suitable solid substrate for fermentation process is a key factor and thus involves the screening of several agro industrial byproducts for microbial growth and amylase production. All the substrates used in the study supported the growth and enzyme formation while wheat bran proved superior to other substrates. A high titre of 330.67 ± 1.372 U/ml amylase was produced when wheat bran was used as the solid substrate during 48h of incubation by *B.megaterium* strain RBJ (Table 1).

The importance of wheat bran for amylase production was previously reported (Baysal et al. 2003; Kunamneni et al. 2005; Mojumdar and Deka 2019) which has promising results, among the various agro industrial substrates used. Widespread suitability of wheat bran may be due to the presence of sufficient nutrients and its ability to remain loose even in moist conditions, thus providing a large surface area (Babu and Satyanarayana 1995).

Byproducts (solid substrates)	Amylase production(U/ml)
Rice bran (RB)	296.33 ± 1.527
Jack fruit seed (JFS)	224.67 ± 1.154
Banana peel (BP)	305.0 ± 1.00
Potato peel (PP)	313.66 ± 0.577
Tamarind seed (TS)	187.0 ± 1.00
Wheat bran (WB)	330.67 ± 1.372
Tapioca peel (TP)	265.23 ± 2.024
Corn cob (CC)	240.33 ± 1.054
Orange peel (OP)	169.0 ± 1.00
Sugarbeet peel (SP)	124.33 ± 0.015

Table 1 Screening of different agricultural byproducts on amylase production by *B. megaterium* strain RBJ through SSF. Each value is the Mean \pm SD of triplicate analysis

Effect of physical parameters on amylase production

Physical parameters such as incubation time, temperature, pH, agitation speed, and moisture content are important in order to promote, stimulate, enhance and optimize the production of amylase by microorganisms. The incubation time is regulated by characteristics of the culture and based on growth rate and enzyme production (Effiom and Sherifat 2019). In the present study, maximum amylase (380.66 ± 0.577 U/ml) production and specific activity (1.82 ± 0.006 U/mg) were obtained during 48h of incubation time at 37°C by *B. megaterium* strain RBJ in solid state fermentation (Fig. 2). The influence of incubation period on amylase production was statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). Similarly, Hassan and AbdKarim (2012) who found that, the highest enzyme activity of *Bacillus subtilis* were 39.9 U/g after 48 h of incubation which is also supported by the study of Yovita et al. (2005) reported that *Bacillus* sp. KP-8104 strain produce maximum enzyme of 140U/g within 48h in SSF containing wheat bran supplemented with 1% NH_4NO_3 and 1% lactose at 37°C .

Fig. 2 Effect of different incubation period on amylase production and its specific activity by *B. megaterium* strain RBJ through SSF

The production of enzyme was determined at different temperatures ranging from 25°C to 45°C and optimum enzyme production was observed at 37°C (Bakri et al. 2012; Gangadharan et

al. 2006; Haq et al. 2009). In the present study, amylase production and its specific activity increased gradually and reached its maximum at 40°C (377.33 ± 1.152 U/ml; 1.93 ± 0.012 U/mg). The influence of temperature on amylase production was statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). The temperature higher than 40°C, amylase production was decreased (Fig. 3). It might be due to that at high temperature the growth of the bacteria was greatly inhibited and enzyme formation was also inhibited (Pandey et al. 2000; Vidyalakshmi et al. 2009).

Fig. 3 Effect of different temperature (°C) on amylase production and its specific activity by *B. megaterium* strain RBJ through SSF

Amylase production by microbial strains strongly depends on the extracellular pH as it influences many enzymatic reactions as well as the transport of various components across the cell membrane (Ellaiah et al. 2002). Maximum amylase production (287.33 ± 0.013 U/ml) and specific activity of 2.03 ± 0.004 U/mg were obtained at pH7, however a decrease in enzyme yield was observed with further increases in pH (Fig 4). The variation in amylase production at different pH was statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). Similar results were observed for *Bacillus* sp. (Devi et al. 2010; Mahdavi et al. 2010, Al Johani et al. 2016).

Fig. 4 Effect of different pH on amylase production and its specific activity by *B. megaterium* strain RBJ through SSF

Agitation intensities of up to 300 rpm have normally been employed to produce amylase from numerous microorganisms (Cui et al. 1997). In the present study, maximum amylase production of 325.67 ± 1.431 U/ml and specific activity of 1.85 ± 0.002 U/mg were recorded at 150 rpm (Fig. 5). The influence of agitation on amylase production was statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). However, Effiom and Sherifat (2019) reported that the growth of *Bacillus* at 200 rpm influenced maximum enzyme production and beyond this rpm, the production was decreased.

Fig. 5 Effect of different agitation speed (rpm) on amylase production and its specific activity by *B.megaterium* strain RBJ through SSF

The inoculum level was also found to be an important factor in the production of amylase. In the present study, the higher (318.33 ± 1.154 U/ml) amylase production and higher specific activity of 2.22 ± 0.016 U/mg were obtained at 1% inoculum in the solid substrate (Fig 6). The variation in amylase production at different inoculums level was statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$). Krishna et al. (2011) reported that 1% inoculum for the banana peel paste was found optimum for SSF for the amylase production and the higher inoculum concentration results in increased moisture content and excess unabsorbed liquid acts as an additional diffusion barrier, which ultimately decreases the growth of the organism as well as the enzyme production.

Fig. 6 Effect of different inoculum size (ml) on amylase production and its specific activity by *B.megaterium* strain RBJ through SSF

Effect of nutritional parameters on amylase production

Anto et al. (2006) reported that supplementation of carbon sources in the form of monosaccharides, disaccharides and polysaccharides resulted in marginal increase in α -amylase production by *B.cereus* during solid-state fermentation using wheat bran and the highest production was observed with glucose. In the present study, maximum (355.33 ± 1.527 U/ml) amylase production and specific activity (2.88 ± 0.01 U/mg) were observed with starch (Table 2).

The function of variation between different carbon sources were statistically more significant ($P < 0.0001$). Similarly, other workers also reported starch as the best carbon source to produce alpha amylase (Gigras et al. 2002; Dharani, 2004).

Amylase production is enhanced with the addition of organic nitrogen sources (Hamilton et al. 1999). Many workers (Anto et al. 2006; Oshoma et al. 2010; Valaparla, 2010) reported that yeast extract as an organic nitrogen source which influences maximum amylase production. In the present study, among the different organic and inorganic nitrogen source tested, peptone was found to be a good nitrogen source for α -amylase production (331.33 ± 1.525 U/ml) and specific activity (2.94 ± 0.025 U/mg) (Table 2). The variation between different nitrogen sources was statistically more significant ($P < 0.0001$). Invariably Bozic et al. (2011) stated that casein was found to be a good nitrogen source for α -amylase production by *B.subtilis* RSKK96.

Carbon sources	Amylase production (U/ml)	Specific activity (U/mg)	Nitrogen sources	Amylase production (U/ml)	Specific activity (U/mg)
Maltose	335.0 ± 1.00	2.48 ± 0.015	Tryptone	292.33 ± 1.124	2.36 ± 0.016
Sucrose	105.0 ± 1.00	0.93 ± 0.009	Casein	294.23 ± 2.364	2.24 ± 0.024
Lactose	117.66 ± 2.364	1.13 ± 0.007	Gelatin	244.66 ± 0.011	1.78 ± 0.023
Fructose	73.33 ± 1.527	0.65 ± 0.003	Peptone	331.33 ± 1.525	2.94 ± 0.025
Glucose	324.23 ± 0.577	2.68 ± 0.021	Beef extract	309.33 ± 1.648	2.53 ± 0.009
Galactose	86.0 ± 1.00	0.84 ± 0.004	Yeast extract	321.0 ± 1.00	2.73 ± 0.034
Starch	355.33 ± 1.527	2.88 ± 0.017	Urea	93.66 ± 0.577	0.92 ± 0.005
Dextrin	215.66 ± 1.648	1.78 ± 0.023	NH_4HPO_4	245.0 ± 1.00	1.86 ± 0.018
Glycerol	202.67 ± 2.844	1.63 ± 0.015	NH_4NO_3	125.33 ± 1.236	1.31 ± 0.004
Xylose	173.32 ± 2.426	1.42 ± 0.016	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	118.0 ± 1.00	1.21 ± 0.014
Mannitol	287.0 ± 1.00	2.44 ± 0.026	NH_4Cl	281.23 ± 0.017	1.98 ± 0.018
Ribose	244.33 ± 2.556	2.18 ± 0.027	NaNO_3	277.33 ± 2.556	2.11 ± 0.009

Control	327.0±1.00	2.63±0.039	KNO ₃	75.67±1.527	0.70±0.003
			Control	305.6 ±1.826	2.41±0.026

Table 2 Effect of carbon and nitrogen sources on amylase production and its specific activity by *B.megaterium* strain RBJ through SSF

Rasooli et al. (2008) pointed out that tryptophan was found to enhance the enzyme production, whereas lysine showed a strong repression on amylase production. In the present study, maximum amylase production (312.66±0.577U/ml) and specific activity (2.80±0.029U/mg) were observed in tryptophan supplemented medium (Table 3). The variation between different amino acids was highly significant (P < 0.0001). In the same way α -amylase production by *B.licheniformis* STCC 6346 was improved with the addition of tryptophan (Vengadaramana et al. 2011).

Supplementation of salts of certain metal ions provided good growth of microorganisms and thereby better enzyme production (Sivaramakrishnan et al. 2006). In the present study, among the tested metal ions, CaCl₂ was found to be suitable for maximizing the amylase production (326.0±1.00U/ml) and its specific activity recorded was 3.15±0.036U/mg (Table 3). The data on amylase production as a function of variation between different metal ions were statistically more significant (F =30307.32; P < 0.0001). Similarly, Rameshkumar and Sovasudha (2011) noted that supplementation of 0.1% CaCl₂ as a mineral source to the medium effectively increased amylase production by *B.subtilis* in solid state fermentation.

Amino acids	Amylase production (U/ml)	Specific activity (U/mg)	Metal ions	Amylase production (U/ml)	Specific activity (U/mg)
Glycin	270.0±2.842	1.99±0.016	MgCl ₂	311.32±1.527	2.83±0.010
L - lysine	162.66±1.527	1.39±0.003	MnCl ₂	302.0±1.00	2.51±0.004
L - tyrosine	237.0 ±1.00	1.63±0.008	FeCl ₂	206.33±2.061	1.46±0.008
L - cystene	303.0±1.00	2.58±0.020	CaCl ₂	326.0±1.00	3.15±0.036
L - alanine	274.32±0.577	2.05±0.022	CoCl ₂	163.0±1.00	1.20±0.012

L - phenylalanine	85.33±1.525	0.57±0.003	ZnCl ₂	95.66±0.577	0.98±0.005
L - isoleucine	97.67±1.342	0.74±0.004	MgSO ₄	264.67±1.154	2.14±0.029
L - valine	131.0±1.00	1.02±0.020	NaCl	285.64±0.014	2.23±0.005
L - methionine	300.65±1.154	2.39±0.009	MnSO ₄	245.33±1.527	1.86±0.018
Tryptophan	312.66±0.577	2.80±0.029	CuSO ₄	221.62±2.024	1.51±0.012
Glutamic acid	243.23±1.527	1.70±0.011	ZnSO ₄	97.67±0.577	1.02±0.006
Control	297.66±1.524	2.25±0.004	HgCl ₂	83.32±1.246	0.68±0.014
			Control	307.0±1.00	2.62±0.15

Table 3 Effect of amino acids and metal ions on amylase production and its specific activity by *B. megaterium* strain RBJ through SSF

Conclusion

Microbial production of amylase is more beneficial than other sources, because it is economical; production quantity is high and can be designed to obtain enzymes of desired characteristics. The present study reports the production of amylase by *B. megaterium* strain RBJ isolated from soil samples near rice mill industries under solid state fermentation of wheat bran. The present work has been taken up with a view to exploring the possibilities of using agro-industrial residues as a starch substrate for the production of amylases by the tested strain in solid state fermentation, which can hydrolyze starch to glucose.

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